

Complex Compounds of Nickel and Copper with 2-Guanidinobenzimidazole*

A. K. Banerjee and S. P. Ghosh

Several complex compounds of nickel and copper with 2-guanidinobenzimidazole have been prepared and their properties studied. Halides, nitrates and sulphates of the complex base, and also the complex hydroxides have been prepared. The complex nickel hydroxide has been obtained in three differently coloured modifications whereas the chloride and sulphate have been obtained in two different colours. All nickel complexes are diamagnetic and hence planar with dsp^2 bonding. The copper complexes do not show any colour change; these are either green or bluish green and paramagnetic ($\mu=1.76$ to 1.83 B.M.).

Ziegelbauer (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1897, I, 9) first obtained a base, $C_8H_9N_5$, by refluxing a mixture of dicyandiamide and *o*-phenylenediamine hydrochloride in ethanol and termed it *o*-phenylenebiguanide.

Pellizzari (*ibid.*, 1921, III, 527) obtained the same base by refluxing a mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine hydrochloride and dicyandiamide in water and represented it as :

Dubsky, Langer and Strand (*Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1938, 10, 103) reported the preparation of two complex compounds of copper and nickel with *o*-phenylenebiguanide having the composition : $(C_8H_9N_5)_2Cu.H_2SO_4.2H_2O$ and $(C_8H_9N_5)_2Ni.H_2SO_4.4H_2O$, represented by (I) or (II).

(I)

(II)

Though the base, $C_8H_9N_5$, resembles biguanide in its reactions with metal ions, it is actually an iminazole derivative and has been wrongly termed as *o*-phenylenebiguanide by the above workers. It has therefore been named 2-guanidinobenzimidazole.

* The "so called" *o*-phenylenebiguanide of Ziegelbauer.

In view of the constitution of metal biguanide complexes advanced by Rây and Saha (this *Journal*, 1937, 14, 670), the above structure for the nickel and copper complexes of 2-guanidinobenzimidazole cannot be justified and it should be represented as :

(where M is a bivalent metal like Cu, Ni, and Co and X is a monovalent anion or its equivalent acid radical).

The nickel complexes have been obtained in differently coloured modifications, viz., brick-red, light pink, and violet. Rây and Chakravarty (*ibid.*, 1941, 18, 609) have obtained with phenylbiguanide, nickel complexes with two different colour modifications. With the present knowledge of these substances it is not possible to assume a cause for the occurrence of such colour modifications. Copper complexes showed no such behaviour. This was also the case with phenylmethylbiguanide (Ghosh and Chatterjee, *ibid.*, 1953, 30, 369) and with *p*-phenethylbiguanide (Ghosh and Banerjee, *ibid.*, 1955, 32, 32). Complexes of copper with biguanide or substituted biguanide are usually rose-red or pink in colour; 2-guanidinobenzimidazole (the so-called *o*-phenylenebiguanide) complexes of copper are, however, green or bluish green and less stable than the biguanide complexes as is evident from the fact that the latter can easily displace 2-guanidinobenzimidazole in its copper complexes. A green variety of copper-phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid was reported by Rây and Dutt (*ibid.*, 1948, 25, 569) with a magnetic moment value of 1.84 B.M.

The nickel complexes are diamagnetic and are square planar with $3d4s4p^2$ bonding. The copper complexes are paramagnetic; their magnetic moments lie between 1.76 and 1.83 B.M. According to Rây and Sen (*ibid.*, 1948, 25, 473), the bonding in the copper complexes should be $4s4p4d^2$. This view is also supported by Craig *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 349).

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Guanidinobenzimidazole was prepared by refluxing a mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine hydrochloride (1 M) and dicyandiamide (2 M) in water for 5 to 6 hours. The precipitated compound was filtered, dissolved in HCl (dil.), and reprecipitated by NaOH. The compound was obtained in plates, m.p. 246-47° (Pelliazari, *loc. cit.*, reports m.p. 245°). (Found: C, 53.69; H, 5.19. $C_8H_9N_5$ requires C, 54.85; H, 5.14%).

Nickel Complexes

α -Nickel-2-guanidinium Benzimidazole Hydroxide.—A dilute solution of NaOH was added dropwise to a solution of nickel chloride (1 M) and 2-guanidinobenzimidazole in HCl (dil.) (2 M), when a light pink precipitate separated, which gradually changed to dirty brick-red on standing. The precipitate was rapidly filtered, washed with cold water and ethanol, and dried over NaOH. (Found: Ni, 11.80; N, 28.10. $[Ni(C_8H_9N_5)_2](OH)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ requires Ni, 11.82; N, 28.18%). It is the most stable of the three varieties. It slowly dissolves in hot water forming a light green solution.

β-Nickel-2-guanidinium Benzimidazole Hydroxide.—When a dilute solution of ammonium hydroxide was substituted for NaOH solution in the above preparation, a light pink variety of the complex base separated. It was washed and dried as before. {Found : Ni, 12.26 ; N, 29.36. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_5)_2](\text{OH})_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 12.31 ; N, 29.37%}.

This variety slowly changes into the α -variety when kept suspended in water or heated over a water bath.

γ-Nickel-2-guanidinium Benzimidazole Hydroxide.—The light pink base, initially obtained in the preparation of the α -complex, was dissolved in HCl (dil.). A little ammonium hydroxide solution was then added, followed by NaOH, when a violet solution was obtained from which a violet precipitate separated on standing. It was washed and dried as above. On drying the colour changed to dirty violet. {Found : Ni, 11.78 ; N, 28.12. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_5)_2](\text{OH})_2, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 11.82 ; N, 28.18%}.

This does not change to the α variety on heating over a water bath. All the different bases liberate ammonia from ammonium salts and are insoluble in hot water.

α-Nickel-2-guanidinium Benzimidazole Chloride.—The complex α -base was suspended in water and was treated with an excess of ammonium chloride on a water bath till the evolution of ammonia had ceased. The yellowish pink precipitate was thoroughly washed with ice-cold water and ethanol and dried in air. {Found : Ni, 11.38 ; Cl, 13.80 ; N, 27.20. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_5)_2]\text{Cl}_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 11.39 ; Cl, 13.76 ; N, 27.14%}.

The chloride is slightly soluble in cold water forming a light green solution. Other complex salts were similarly prepared by metathesis of the complex base with the respective ammonium salt.

β-Nickel-2-guanidinium benzimidazole chloride is orange in colour. (Found : Ni, 11.32. Calc. Ni, 11.39%).

The orange-coloured β -chloride, when suspended in water and heated on a water bath, changed to the yellowish pink α -variety.

α-Nickel-2-guanidinium Benzimidazole Bromide and Iodide.—The bromide was obtained in yellowish pink colour. {Found : Ni, 9.18 ; Br, 25.10. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_5)_2]\text{Br}_2, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 9.16 ; Br, 24.97%}. The β - and γ -bases on similar treatment gave the same yellowish pink α -bromide. The iodide is pink in colour. {Found : Ni, 8.40 ; I, 36.48. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_5)_2]\text{I}_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 8.41 ; I, 36.35%}.

α-Nickel-2-guanidinium Benzimidazole Sulphates.—The complex α -sulphate was obtained by metathesis of the base with ammonium sulphate in brick-red colour. {Found : Ni, 10.48 ; SO_4 , 17.54. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_5)_2]\text{SO}_4, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 10.50 ; SO_4 , 17.18%}. From the β -base the sulphate was obtained in yellowish buff colour. {Found : Ni, 10.22 ; SO_4 , 16.70. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_5)_2]\text{SO}_4, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 10.17 ; SO_4 , 16.64%}.

The β -sulphate, when suspended in water and heated on a water bath, changed to the brick-red α -variety. The γ -base, however, on similar treatment yielded the brick-red coloured α -sulphate.

α-Nickel-2-guanidinium benzimidazole nitrate was obtained in dirty red colour. {Found : Ni, 10.69 ; N, 30.59. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_5)_2](\text{NO}_3)_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 10.66 ; N, 30.50%}.

Copper Complexes

Copper-2-guanidinium Benzimidazole Hydroxide.—To a solution of copper sulphate (1 M) and 2-guanidinobenzimidazole (2 M) in HCl (dil.) a dilute solution of NaOH was added dropwise

avoiding excess, when an olive-green precipitate was formed. The green precipitate was quickly filtered, washed with cold water, and dried over NaOH. {Found: Cu, 12.63; N, 27.98. $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_5)_2](\text{OH})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 12.72; N, 28.06%}.

The base is moderately soluble in hot water. It liberates ammonia from ammonium salts; when neutralised with dilute mineral acids, corresponding complex salts are produced.

The salts of the complex copper-2-guanidinium benzimidazole base were obtained by the action of the corresponding ammonium salt on the base. The salts are paramagnetic. Colour and analyses of the complex salts are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Complex salts of Cu.	Colour.	Formula.	%Copper.		%Anion.		μ (B.M.)
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	
Chloride	Deep green	X. $\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	10.50	10.40	Cl: 11.60	11.62	1.82
Bromide	Dark ..	X. $\text{Br}_2 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	10.30	10.31	Br: 26.07	25.93	1.82
Iodide	.. .	X. $\text{I}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	9.01	9.01	I: 36.17	36.13	1.83
Nitrate	Bluish ..	X. $(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	10.43	10.41	N: 26.75	27.56	1.79
Sulphate	X. $\text{SO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	11.21	11.27	SO_4 : 17.04	17.05	1.76

* X = $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_5)_2]$

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PATNA UNIVERSITY.

Received November 17, 1960.